

SZ-SB-III-01-01 Self-Assessment-Test and search for a tutor (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091416
ID	SZ-SB-III-01-01
Title	Self-Assessment-Test and search for a tutor
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Mark - Pupil https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13643228
Short description	Mark is taking a self-assessment test and is looking for a tutor to help him with math.
Result	Mark identifies his learning deficits and contacts a tutor.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Find and conduct self-assessment"• Part 2: "Find a tutor at BIRD"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Mark is registered and logged in at BIRD• the tutor XY is registered and logged in at BIRD
Components	#data-wallet #chat #buddyfinder #learningpathfinder
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Mark Engel is about to graduate. He is currently in 10th grade of middle school and is struggling with math. His teacher strongly recommends that he starts getting tutoring to improve. Math is one of the four subjects in the middle school diploma that require a final exam, so it's important for him to improve.

Problem definition

Mark is struggling with math and needs tutoring. He's also unsure whether he's just missing the 10th-grade material or whether his deficits are more extensive. The fact that he doesn't know where his deficits start lets him feel very insecure.

Background and context

Mark mostly gets good grades, except in math. According to his teacher, he has deficits there. At the same time, math is one of his exam subjects. Even though he doesn't yet know what he wants to do later on and whether his math grade will be important, he wants to pass the exam with good grades.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Mark is worried that he might not have fully grasped the material from the previous class and is therefore currently struggling with math. He can't estimate the extent of his deficits and how long it will take to make up for them. Mark is ambitious but shy. He doesn't dare to explain his situation to the teacher or ask her for advice.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Mark has been searching the internet for online tutoring, but hasn't found what he's looking for. On the one hand, the range of offerings is very large, and on the other hand, they are sorted by grade level, but Mark doesn't know exactly what he needs to catch up on. He feels disoriented.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Find and conduct self-assessment"

Step 1: After Mark receives a hint from his math teacher that he needs to catch up in math, he first looks for a self-assessment test on BIRD to identify his weaknesses.

Step 2: Mark opens the LearningPathFinder and enters the following in the search: "Mathematics Self-Test".

Step 3: The LearningPathFinder generates a list of results, which Mark browses. He quickly finds what he's looking for and clicks on the offer. This redirects him to the provider's website, where he logs in using SSO. [Years 10 and 11 in the OnlineDiagnose - OnlineDiagnose](#)

Step 4: After Mark completes the self-assessment test, he is offered the option to send the results to his wallet. He agrees because he might be able to present the results during tutoring.

Step 5: When Mark returns to the home page, a tooltip alerts him to the possibility of finding a tutor using the Buddy Finder.

Part 2: "Find a tutor at BIRD"

Step 1: Mark is curious, clicks on the tool tip and opens the Buddy Finder.

Step 2: In the Buddy Finder search, he looks for a suitable tutor by entering the following information:

- State: Saxony
- City: Dresden
- Educational Area: School
- Subject: Mathematics
- Further Information: Algebra
- Tutor/Peer: Tutor
- Individual or Group: Individual
- Male or Female: open

Step 4: The Buddy Finder generates a list of results based on the search query, which Mark then goes through.

Step 5: Mark selects the person who has the most matches to his search query and sends a contact request.

Step 6: Mark receives a message that his request has been confirmed. He opens the chat between him and tutor XY, briefly introduces himself, and explains his request.